

Abstract

A reason for the existence of souls is given. Origin of life, consciousness, emotions, coupling of souls and bodies is discussed based on previous research. Some questions are answered and additional questions asked regarding the phenomena.

No origin

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1 Intro

Some believe that consciousness emerges with increasing complexity of a neural network and some even believe that this network does not have to be biological. Such are the views of reductionists. From a broader point of view, based on Complete Relativity[1] (CR), I argue that consciousness is an evolving phenomenon whose local *roots* can be traced to the coupling of *elementary* particles with mass. The complexity of this *particle* or superposition of particles is correlated with body complexity. I refer to this quantum of energy as soul and I find the soul-body coupling necessary for consciousness.

It may be possible for machines or algorithms to become conscious, but this requires coupling or strong entanglement of the machine with a soul and probability for the coupling of souls and inorganic matter is probably extremely low.

I consider individual atoms and molecules as living beings (albeit extremely introverted), so the term inorganic is relative.

Any kind of organization should be coupled to a hallucination or superposition of hallucinations, embodying it. However, this is not soul-body coupling, this is coupling between bodies on different scales (dimensions), or in different moments in time. Even though information exchange will exist between these (unless the body is frozen in time, but nothing absolutely is), unless coupled to a localized distinct soul (*carrier* of consciousness) strongly entangled with the collective, this organization is not a conscious individual.

However, consciousness has layers. In one interpretation, weak localization may be correlated with subconscious operation, which can be a precursor to localization. Instinct may be generally explained as a result of coded past

experience but deeper layers of consciousness (subconsciousness) probably are, at least in some species or individuals, effectively correlated with events in the future.

According to CR, nothing can be exempt from relativity, including causality. Excretion of hormones on one scale is thus relatively synchronized with a feeling on the other scale and since coupling [of scales] is required it's generally meaningless to argue which phenomena is the cause and which is the effect. However, since synchronization must be relative, in some reference frames a noticeable delay will be present and one will precede the other.

Due to lack of relativity in widely accepted theories and stubborn beliefs in well-established *facts*, modern science is still far from understanding life, to quote a well known Croatian scientist Nenad Raos:

"All things considered, something has been dissolving, drying, dissolving again repeatedly who knows how many millions of times - and at the end something like a living cell emerged."
[2]

However, with all due respect, all things considered, life did not emerge - it is the result of entanglement between different scales of energy and it couldn't have been absolutely spontaneous either.

It is only the amount of consciousness that is proportional to quantized correlation between entangled scales.

In that case, the same soul could be coupling to different species of life with different incarnations - difference would be simply in amount of consciousness which may be correlated with genetic coding.

However, while organizational complexity may be proportional to the amount of consciousness (intelligence), the expression of that intelligence, by my hypotheses, is not limited to extroversion.

In fact, increasing amount of consciousness may be proportional to increase in introversion, in which case, the species will be losing means for extroverted expression. This can be interpreted as a requirement for conservation of relativity. In example, one might consider whales as less intelligent than humans, but with greater brain complexity their consciousness is simply largely introverted and from certain reference frames they are more intelligent.

2 Theory

If everything is completely relative, there can be no absolute immortality, however, relative immortality has to [relatively] exist. This is why everything has to die, but also implies that nothing can die completely.

Nothing can be absolutely equal either so differences in the amount of death (loss of consciousness) between lifeforms will exist. Birth simply must be a relative inflation of life, while death is deflation. Amount of death will be proportional to strength of coupling between the body and a soul. Strong coupling should imply faster evolution, while weak coupling should imply slower experience of time. Thus, [relatively] uncoupled souls will experience no time, relatively. Consciousness here is never absolutely lost, it gets *diluted* on one scale for uncoupled souls but increases on the other.

The moment of initiation of life is the moment of coupling, when the soul waveform starts collapsing into a well-defined lifeform (distinct identity). With increasing mass and inflation of the body, the soul is concentrating in space and evolving in time, raising local consciousness. This is synchronized with the *ignition* of smaller scale lifeforms (components of the body) which *mirror* the operation of the distinct quantum of consciousness (operating in time) as a network of entangled micro-conscious entities distributed over larger space.

Note that the collapse is equivalent not only to wave-function collapse in quantum mechanics, but also to acquisition of mass. However, in Complete Relativity (CR), the particle is never absolutely massless, even in a waveform when it's energy is typically equalized with frequency.

The two entities (relative space and relative time) co-evolve, influencing each other in oscillating manner, more or less influenced, physically and mentally, by external factors (waveforms/lifeforms) - souls are more or less polarized and more or less sensitive to gravitational and electro-magnetic forces of particular scale and frequencies of field excitation.

Soul, in my works, is defined as a graviton[3].

3 A bottle of consciousness and a bag of emotions

In modern science, consciousness and feelings are not properly defined, at best, both are assumed to emerge (from where?) *simply* with increase in complexity of physical interactions and expression.

However, as noted before, there are some missing links here.

While consciousness and feelings may be synchronized [or even relatively induced] with physical awareness (reaction to action) and excretion of hormones, it is obvious that these are not equivalents, otherwise, artificial machines would be conscious [and actually intelligent] and electrochemical reactions in a bottle would be isolated (bottled) emotions (who would feel them, the bottle?).

Clearly, mental and physical are two different domains of reality and require localization and coupling to form a conscious and emotional individual.

Through my research, I have recognized the relatively non-physical (mental) matter in quanta of space - each characterized and localized by its gravitational maximum, which I consider to be an appropriate synonym for a soul.

For a body to be alive, it is necessary, for it to be coupled with a soul.

One might ask why do we feel our personality localized in our head (brain), why not in our stomach, for example?

The answer might be the fact that sensory organs are connected to the brain. But this is not only the place where we feel physical stimuli, we feel mental here also. Why are our eyes, ears, nose and tongue all located on our head, close to brain? The only sensor not strongly localized to head is skin. Why aren't at least our mouth (tongue) and nose closer to our stomach?

Perhaps this is more optimized configuration, but obviously, evolution is localizing our sensors to brain area.

As I have hypothesized elsewhere, if progressive evolution continues, this will lead to loss of limbs and result in a spherical life form, coupled with loss of physical sensitivity and increase in energy of mental mechanics.

I have also hypothesized that a collective of organs in an organism is a result of *fossilization* of organismic symbiosis through evolution (mainly in strong evolution pulses).

It is thus likely that all our organs once had their own sensory organs (eg. mouths), but evolution [naturally] selected sensors of the brain organ to continue evolving, while others were subdued. A navel is the obvious remnant of a stomach's mouth - it is still used to feed babies before they get born. But why was the brain selected over all other organ[ism]s?

Due to the fact that physical abilities are receding, it has to be it's mental capabilities (oscillation of life between extroverted and introverted forms implies this selection).

However, this selection was occurring millions and millions of years ago when the brain was not complex. That is a big problem for the interpretation of consciousness as emerging from physical complexity.

Obviously, mental phenomena do not emerge from physical, they co-evolve (if one insists on emergence, it can only be relative - understood as exponential increase in amount of consciousness).

If one observes the collective of souls of human organism as a [collective of souls in a] carbon atom, the convergence becomes logical - after initial inflation into diverse organisms, the system is imploding and gravitating toward the [bary]centre.

Only once this is established, nature and mechanics of universes (life) become clear - logical and intuitive. The advancement of science, however, does not only bring answers, it generally brings more questions too. In this case, questions might be:

- when does the coupling of a soul and body occur?
- what are the requirements for such coupling?
- etc.

I have tried to answer some of these questions myself, here and in other work.

4 Consciousness and memory

Law of energy conservation dictates that, as a form of energy, consciousness cannot be created out of nothing. This is a consequence of complete relativity - creation must be relative, it is always a sum of horizontal and vertical transformation (inflation/deflation) of energy. But neither component is ever absolutely zero. This implies that all [species of] energies ever *created* exist on different scales relatively simultaneously (differences exist in the *point* of evolution, relative future of one scale must exist as relative present on other scale) and individual quanta of energy inflate or deflate to another [vertical] energy level at time of *creation*.

In the event of transition some amount of memory is lost, but none is absolutely lost - it is simply not strongly coupled to the individual any more.

Generally, energy is oscillating between scales, so, during weak evolution, there is a high probability one will reincarnate in a body of the same scale.

There can be no absolutely infinite nor absolutely constant number of available scales, and this is another reason why everything must die eventually and why different lifetimes (or time dilation) must exist between scales.

Note that, according to my hypotheses, coupling of a body with a soul is coupling with a distinct gravitational well and its associated time (time = small scale space).

A lifeform, thus, starts ageing as a distinct individual once the body is coupled with a soul.

Things get complicated with souls/bodies in symbiosis when multiple organ[isms] form a larger distinct organ[ism]. In that case, different parts of the body may age differently and one maximum (soul) may be dominant, but, individuality becomes less localized and effectively so does consciousness too.

4.1 Anatomy of a living brain

A brain is a central processing unit (CPU) of a living organism. On its own, it is a deterministic machine with massively parallelized processing. It contains components connected through input/output channels to receptors of sensory

organs forming the system of awareness. This is further connected with circuitry correlated with consciousness and subconsciousness.

However, all these systems are quantized into individual cells and proteins - it is an eco-system consisting of multiple organisms in symbiosis.

Obviously, brain is not strongly localized in space but it is in time.

However, our consciousness is strongly localized in space (we don't feel quantized all over the body or the brain - we feel strong individuality) but not so much in time.

Thus, this [overall] deterministic machine in a living individual must be coupled with a quantum system where the brain and its activity is mirrored but compressed in space - enabling strong sense of individuality.

Figure 1: Cross-section of a brain/soul system model (brain/soul not to scale)

An ideal case of brain/soul symbiosis is shown on Fig. 1. Brain mass is a 3-dimensional structure containing multiple quanta of living individuals exchanging and processing information, all concentrated about the radius R_{re} .

While quanta of brain mass may number billions of particularum, in the same environment the soul is in a bosonic state - localized to 2-dimensional area (sphere surface in neutral form) at radius R_{img} , effectively representing a single quantum in space. Difference between R_{re} and R_{img} may generally be in multiple orders of magnitude, but not in *ideal* cases.

In any case, while quanta forming awareness, consciousness and subconsciousness in the brain are separated in space, the 3 quanta of Awareness, Consciousness and Subconsciousness of the soul are separated in time.

The radii of induced gravitons are at times also the radii of real gravitons, mostly during formation, however, most likely, these energy levels are occasionally (or periodically) occupied by real gravitons [for relatively short periods of time] even in adult life (eg. during adult neurogenesis or, events of soul-body synchronization). At these events, the strength of coupling of the soul and body is decreased - consciousness is less localized, therefore, the process likely occurs during hibernation or sleep.

Due to requirements of [complete] relativity, the vertical universes (scales of energy) are self-similar and the process cannot be limited to one scale. The ignition of stars in a galaxy is the large scale evidence for this process. In a typical adult galaxy, the central black hole event horizon is the radius of the real graviton (the soul).

In the Solar System, the outer event horizon of the Sun forms the soul of that system (in CR, event horizons are relative - not necessarily *black* and none are absolutely *black*).

4.1.1 Distance from perfection

In absolutely ideal case, R_{re} and R_{img} would be equal and the organism would have a shape of a perfect sphere. This is impossible. In reality, the ideal case represents such brain/soul entanglement where the scale of both is of the same order of magnitude.

Distance from perfection is relative and may be defined as a ratio of elementary particularum required to shape the body and those forming the soul.

If one defines atom as an elementary particula, distance of a human body from perfection is $> 10^{27}$.

However, better definition is the ratio of R_{re} and R_{img} (eccentricity), eg. for spherical bodies:

$$d = \sqrt{1 - \frac{R_{img}^2}{R_{re}^2}}$$

If one wants to be precise, distance from perfection is distance [in gravity] from gravity of a perfect sphere. This can be mathematically expressed using Ricci flows on Riemannian manifolds (as in GR), or simply:

$$\int_{t=0}^T \sqrt{(dg_e - dg)^2}$$

where $g = g(t)$ is a gravitational (or generally - energy) potential of a perfectly spherical source (soul), $g_e = g_e(t)$ is the effective potential, t is the distance from the soul in space (time). For a natural (3-dimensional) metric, $t = (t_0, t_1, t_2)$.

T is the distance of correlation.

Due to conservation of relativity, bodies or gravitational wells of souls do not have absolute surface limits and quanta of a body or a soul can be entangled with distant quanta of bodies (souls).

However, for most practical purposes, T may be limited to the surface [discontinuity] or a Hill sphere (discontinuity) of a body/soul.

Obviously, comparing individuals of the same species, mass (weight) will generally be proportional to distance from perfection.

Perfection is not proportional to intelligence (although low intelligence generally leads to more weight[4] and a decrease in grey matter[5]) but will generally be proportional to energy efficiency, due to decrease in energy spent on maintenance.

Consider a star with one dwarf planet in orbit and the same star with a gas giant in orbit - the latter will be radiating and absorbing more energy than the former. The same is true when comparing skinny and overweight people of the same species.

Note how *lepton* mass oscillation in planetary systems is present also in human systems - in overweight people some organs are larger (kidneys, liver, pancreas) while some are smaller (brain) when compared to skinny people, whereas white matter of the brain does not change (which probably indicates stronger correlation of white matter with the soul - Sun equivalent).

Calculating distance from perfection is useful if one wants to know how far away one is from a discrete energy level - as, generally, these levels are closest to absolute perfection.

5 Fossilization of relative abstraction

A parallel to soul/matter relations can be found in human organizations.

Every human organization or institution is embodied in one or more particles (people), however, at least in ideal case, each functions as a single body.

Behaviour of that body is determined by the consensus reached by multiple particles or by a decision of a single particle (consensus of a smaller scale).

If this *abstract* organ[isation|ism] behaves as a single body, it effectively is a single body, although, it is clear that, like a piece of rock, does not have a unique distinct soul (or at least not overly conscious one on that scale).

However, if that organization is increasing its freedom with the decrease of freedom of individual constitutional particles, the same system is likely *attracting* (inflating) a distinct soul.

Particles and groups of particles, all connected mentally through symbiosis (even if asymmetric one), thus become precursor proteins, cells or organs of this future organism.

After all, in CR, mental connections (entanglements) are relatively mental, they are certainly physical on smaller scale.

Although, with relativity in cause and effect, it is equally valid to say that it is the upcoming incarnation of the soul that is inducing creation of such precursor entanglements.

In each universe, there is an effectively attracting force acting between past and future, eventually resulting in a pulse of strong evolution synchronizing the evolution of the system of mentally (symbiotically) connected matter *from the past* with the soul *from future*, coupling them into a single organism.

The future here does not represent local future, the soul does not travel through local time as it might be implied, it is simply more evolved - coming, with the death of an individual, from a more evolved [distant] environment, so it only effectively *arrives from the future*.

The future of human kind, in this context, is described in more detail in paper analysing the Solar System[6] in context of CR, and in Judgment day 6[7] paper.

6 The moment[um] of coupling

But how and when exactly does the coupling of matter and soul occur?

Obviously, either some real mechanism of attraction between a particular soul and particular matter has to exist or an effective one - like synchronicity (here effective does not mean unreal, rather attraction with no apparent force).

Synchronicity may be interpreted as effective attraction between phenomena, with no apparent force (at least not in standard space).

Generally, if two oscillating entities are decreasing distance and are *aware* of each other (radiating energy of the same scale), both will be adjusting frequencies to match each other and the system will converge to shared resonance.

But if *we* reverse the arrow of time, it is the resonance that causes attraction (or non-resonance that causes repulsion), and this interpretation is, due to relativity of cause and effect, valid in CR.

Assuming that physical manifestation of the soul is equal to future physical manifestation of the body (eg. with DNA execution), albeit on different scale, the coupling could be interpreted as attraction between past and future. The soul, however, should resemble the body of a past incarnation at the moment of coupling, and, between coupling, it is [relatively] agnostic to time - just as time of the observable universe (large scale soul) effectively started flowing at the moment of inflation (due to coupling with even larger scale matter).

This is thus a coupling of relative future with relative past and the probability for such coupling will be proportional to similarity of bodies be-

tween incarnations. But the soul may oscillate inter-species also, where probability for coupling and its stability will be higher for harmonics. However, considering that development and growth of a body is effectively a lossy compressed past evolution which includes different species over time and if these are all harmonics, the initial coupling of a soul with any body can be interpreted as inter-species coupling. Note that, in bosonic (or Bose-Einstein) condensates, the [collapse to] ground state can be interpreted as manifestation of [attraction of] resonance. The electro-magnetic attraction and repulsion can then be explained with interacting photons (forming magnetic field tubes) condensing into resonance and exploding out of resonance, respectively. Resonance in space is thus the effect of decreasing distance, while in time, resonance is a force decreasing distance. The same is true for quantum entanglement.

A naked soul is a gravitational maximum (*dark matter* maximum) with its associated gravitational field and can exist on different discrete scales.

Clearly, every [relatively] elementary particula having a gravitational maximum coupled with a body of matter is alive (non-coupled or naked particulae are naked souls, forming dark matter).

On discrete elementary scales of invariance, attracting force is gravitational and electro-magnetic (ratio depending on polarization of a maximum and its space).

Fusion of particularum into atoms and molecules thus has to be a symbiosis (entanglement) of different, in this case introverted, organismorum.

In introverted organisms, intelligence and behaviour is expressed mentally, in soul space, rather than in physical space. In extremely introverted organisms, awareness is decoupled from consciousness, and, without external expression of intelligence, such organisms may be considered non-intelligent or dead matter by extroverted forms of life. Note that coupling (birth) and decoupling (death) of soul and matter enables effects of quantum mechanics, such as quantum tunnelling and dual nature.

All our organs are thus a result of *hard wiring* of symbiosis of different organisms, and, since we feel strong individuality, this coupling has to have, apart from individual souls [of organs], a unique discrete soul where that individuality is localized.

According to my research, largest gravitational maximum is in the centre of a brain, but all other organs have their discrete maximums and a particular

amount of consciousness even if, by multiple orders of magnitude, lower.

Our soul seems to be the scaled carbon atom soul, as configuration and number of vital organs correspond with that of the carbon atom. A human who loses a vital organ (or it is yet to develop it) is equivalent to a neutral carbon atom losing an electron - it becomes polarized and starts attracting other souls of the scale which would here differentiate into the missing organ.

Assuming human soul is the [equivalent of a] carbon atom soul, what is its scale?

In my other works, I have concluded it is of a photon (U_{-1}) scale, however, whether its space (time) is stretched as we grow and quanta of the soul become souls of vital organs (most massive one in the brain area), or it remains localized (in the central region of the brain) and only entangled with souls [of organs] it evolves in symbiosis with, remains an open question.

However, if ageing of organs is not synchronized to a certain degree, like in the case of an adult man losing the vital organ (new one would have to develop from ground up while others are already mature), death - decoupling of soul systems from matter with a change in spin momentum, is imminent.

On our scale, polarized people usually seek an organ donor, and the already mature differentiated organ is surgically (by force) implanted into the body - they have *evolved* to do the same as a polarized mature carbon atom does, for billions of years already.

It is clear now why organs come with some habits and preferences - these are the manifestation of memory and consciousness of the donated living organ.

The equivalence of organs and organisms enables the creation of chimeric organisms (hybrids) - it is possible, for example, to grow a human organ inside the pig, the only condition being that the stem cells are synchronized in development.

Unlike for elementary (mentally complex) particularum, it is hard to say when and how does a particular soul couple with a particular physically complex particula such as human body.

It may be during embryonic or fetal stage of development, but, most likely, coupling occurs with the egg some time before fertilization, albeit, at that point, consciousness is extremely low or extremely introverted. Further development likely involves many events of soul energy level change and perhaps even complete decoupling of soul and matter, resetting most soul memory except memories embodied into instinct.

7 The resonance

Although I have arrived at the conclusion in a different way, my idea that everything is alive and has some degree of consciousness is not new. In fact, the idea is apparently very old and embodied into panpsychism.

Also, there are other theories on consciousness. The one I find closest to mine is the General Resonance Theory[8] (GRT).

While I can agree that shared resonance of micro-conscious entities (eg. resonant electro-magnetic activity of neurons in the brain) will form one part of a macro-conscious entity and may even reflect the distinct macro-consciousness, this does not solve the problem of strong spatial localization of consciousness and absolute death in space. I also cannot agree that this is one-directional (micro-conscious entities affecting macro, but not vice versa).

In my theory, which may be referred to as Body-Soul Coupling Theory (BST), the consciousness of an individual is *only* entangled with shared resonance of micro-conscious entities but it has a distinct, [by orders of magnitude] more localized manifestation. Such, that it is elementary relative to the body - it's own constituent micro-conscious entities cannot be resolved by the very interpretation of the lifeform in nature's processor on deterministic scale.

This entanglement of body and soul can be interpreted as symbiosis (or at least co-evolution) of small scale and large scale energy and such symbiosis is likely the requirement for any lifeform to have distinct consciousness - to be alive to any degree, at a particular scale.

Note that the soul of a macro-individual should be centred in the shared resonance of micro-conscious entities and the volumetric expansion of the collective should be correlated with changes in soul momentum.

Operation on two scales of reality (space and time) is thus the requirement for life and, if everything operates in both space and time, everything is alive, something more on one scale something more on the other.

I consider photons (of *zero-point* energy) and graviton neutrinos as particles forming souls of human scale.

8 Additional evidence for soul-body interaction

Recently, the study on rats revealed that brain maps its position within the environment onto a toroidal manifold[9] (positions on the torus correspond to positions of the moving animal in the environment). This is very interesting, as I have hypothesized previously that the general shape of a graviton (soul) is a torus[10].

I have also hypothesized that this shape changes with soul polarization - in strongly polarized souls the shape should be ring-like while in strongly neutral

souls it should be more spherical (albeit still having holes on the poles).

Indeed, the same study notes that ring-like manifolds have been discovered in fruit flies, as well as in mammals.

Further studies could provide additional evidence. Per my hypotheses, species can generally be divided into sub-species depending on polarization, although species may be dominantly polarized (as human species currently) or dominantly neutral (as some wild animals).

Additional studies could prove this. I believe comparison between humans and cetaceans could reveal interesting results.

Additional evidence, is, however, also provided in my other[11] works[12].

8.1 Evidence in peculiar personality changes

After her father died, my mother became more like him (considering epigenetics). After his mother died, my father became more like her. These changes may not be permanent but after a couple of years they are still evident. It's hard to attribute that to pure coincidence.

Death either triggered change or was synchronized with that change. Epigenetic changes synchronized with death of a parent may be normal, however, why would they cause relative imitation of that parent?

This synchronicity has two interpretations:

- it is the evidence for existence of souls where upon death the soul of deceased either permanently coupled with the soul of a close relative or it triggered a change in dominant personality in a close relative so it is more aligned with the personality of the deceased,
- the moment of death is genetically coded and inherited by children to trigger expression of genes inherited by the parent at the moment that parent dies.

Now the rough life expectancy can be extrapolated from DNA, but does genetic information really carries precise moments of death of our ancestors, even those who haven't died yet?

This could be understandable if one always dies at the same age as their parent did (which one?) so time of death inherited is not encoded future rather past that is likely to repeat.

But that is not the case, our DNA is a mixture of DNA from both parents and time of death can be significantly different (our parents rarely die at the same time).

Therefore, one has to discard the possibility that this is genetically coded in the body.

We could be genetically programmed to react in a specific way at the time of death of a parent but how does the body knows when one of our parents dies and which one died?

There is no other way but to associate this with consciousness. But we generally do not imitate our parents consciously! Thus, this is mentally induced relatively permanent and very specific change in gene expression.

I see no more elegant solution to this than changes in entanglement between particles (souls) which then induces epigenetic changes in the correlated body, probably in a cascading chain reaction.

Upon death, it is probably the spin momentum of the soul (graviton) that inverts and this inversion is reflected in the child.

I have previously hypothesized that our soul is a superposition of [at least] two souls - one correlated with a genome of ancestors, one with descendants. Inversion of spin in either one will affect total spin and this change will be reflected in the epigenome.

Generally, during life, gene expression may oscillate between ancestry and progeny and this may be synchronized with oscillation of spin in the soul correlated with progeny. The other soul (correlated with ancestors) inverts only at the time of death of a parent with whom that soul is correlated with.

Obviously, our soul may be a superposition of 3 (so it includes both parents) or more souls (depending on magnitude of progeny).

Some lag between the body and the soul is also likely and at times the epigenome may be a superposition of ancestral and progenial epigenome. And this is what makes us unique.

Causality in CR is relative. It can be said that we are affected by both our ancestors and descendants (past and future) but it can also be said that we affected our ancestors and descendants even before we were born.

This is all possible with the existence of souls acting as quantum particles. Without souls we would be unable to evolve new characteristics and we probably wouldn't oscillate in expression either. Applying regression, obviously our parents couldn't be different from each other so we would all be [unconscious] clones. But regressing further, it is obvious we couldn't even exist because our first ancestor would have to be a clone of nothing.

One could argue that a changing environment could make us evolve new characteristics.

Environment can affect both genome (eg. radiation exposure can induce gene mutation) and epigenome (but probably hardly if one isn't conscious).

Note that one can simply equalize consciousness with the soul and then argue whether this soul (consciousness) has to have a distinct physical interpretation. By those who believe we are absolutely deterministic machines this physical interpretation is the brain. For others, who believe in relativity, the soul must be a quantum of life (consciousness) coupled to this relatively deterministic relative machine.

If the soul provides consciousness, without it, we are nothing but machines, a resource that cannot be molded into a living *thing* no matter how random and

big are the modifications.

We shouldn't even be needing evidence that souls exist - we should ask for evidence that they don't. And it's hard to believe this evidence could ever be provided because, in absolute determinism, the evidence would have to consist of billions of [inorganic] transistors and other synthetic materials that together completely emulate a living conscious being, showing emotions and everything else one can associate with such beings, including the ability to mate and produce offspring. Offspring that is different from parents but can also produce offspring so the species of this thing are evolving over time adapting to environment and doing all other things life usually does - easily.

Good luck with that. Oh yeah, for some reason, no one's trying. Because creation of complex machines is hard. Creation of life, on the other hand, is extremely easy when one has all the ingredients. If it ain't easy [from the start] it ain't creation of life - one is missing something. I call it soul.

9 Conclusion

Life does not have an absolute origin and neither does consciousness - it does not emerge from non-living matter. Each component of life is alive and an individual form of life is always a coupling of a an living eco-system with a distinct soul. It evolves through *fossilization* of weak symbiosis of different forms of smaller scale life into a strong symbiosis of organs [at some scale].

Note that, during symbiosis *fossilization*, organisms becoming organs lose some organs themselves (limbs, mostly) as these become unnecessary. This makes it clear that progressive evolution leads to increasing introversion of life - reality for that life is increasingly becoming the expression of interactions of a lower scale (becoming virtual relative to external world), it is decreasing external expression, becoming more and more isolated from the outer environment, essentially, becoming elementary - relatively, of course, to that external world.

This *fossilization* starts with the moment of coupling of a large scale soul with the system in symbiosis.

Thus, a relatively weak and strong evolution of life is possible, ignited by pulses of soul/matter coupling of different scales, and with polarized life being least sustainable.

If the soul of an individual is a quantum of space (time) of its host (god[13]), obviously, the capacity for life is limited.

Death is, thus, for life, more important than life itself - not only it is necessary for survival and evolution of life, it is required for birth of new life.

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